

&constants

/

&model

model_type = 'EVOL' ! Obtain stellar structure from an evolutionary model
file = 'evo_Msun=1.3.mesa' ! File name of the evolutionary model
file_format = 'MESA' ! File format of the evolutionary model

/

&mode

l = 1 ! Harmonic degree
m = 0

/

&osc

outer_bound = 'VACUUM' ! Use a zero-pressure outer mechanical boundary condition

/

&num

diff_scheme = 'COLLOC_GL4' ! 4th-order collocation scheme for difference equations

/

&scan

grid_type = 'INVERSE' ! Scan for modes using a uniform-in-period grid; best for g modes
freq_min = 35 ! Minimum frequency to scan from
freq_max = 550 ! Maximum frequency to scan to
freq_min_units = 'UHZ'
freq_max_units = 'UHZ'
n_freq = 5000 ! Number of frequency points in scan

/

&grid

alpha_osc = 20 ! Ensure at least 10 points per wavelength in propagation regions
alpha_exp = 10 ! Ensure at least 2 points per scale length in evanescent regions
n_inner = 15 ! Ensure at least 5 points between center and inner turning point

/

&ad_output

summary_file = 'summary.txt' ! File name for summary file
summary_file_format = 'TXT' ! Format of summary file
summary_item_list = 'M_star,R_star,l,n_pg,omega,E_norm' ! Items to appear in summary file
mode_template = 'mode.%J.txt' ! File-name template for mode files
mode_file_format = 'TXT' ! Format of mode files
mode_item_list = 'l,n_pg,omega,x,xi_r,xi_h' ! Items to appear in mode files

/

&nad_output

/